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Loss of immunosurveillance in TNBC.

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This paper describes cardinal changes in innate and adaptive immunity and natural killer cell function in TNBC. We previously described other aspects of immunodeficiency in TNBC including deficiency in IL2RG.

1 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.
2 We used the normal breast transcriptome as a reference transcriptome for differential expression analysis.

3 **Results**

4 Figure 1: ACADSB and ACSS3 were induced, as were SCOC and SDR16C5.

5 Figure 2: Steroid metabolism in TNBC: We observed activation of AKR1C1 and AKR1C3, DHRS24 and
6 DHRS7b, and Hsdb family genes including 17b8 and 11b2, as well as HSDL1.

7 **Self non-self recognition in TNBC**

8 Figure 3: LY6D was silenced, as was Ly96, and LY6E expression was significantly reduced.

9 Figure 4: Expression of AIF1 was also silenced.

10 Figure 5: LSP and EPSTI1 were repressed, but TSLP, SDF2 and less significantly, STAG3L4 were
11 activated.

12 **Antiviral signaling and the interferon system in the primary tumor in TNBC**

13 Figure 6: OASL and OAS2 expression was also reduced, and OAS1 reduction was weak but perceptible.

14 Figure 7: LCP1/2 reduction, with previously described IL2RG silencing.

15 Figure 8: This was coupled with loss soluble interferons IFNE and IFNG, as well as IFNB1.

16 Figure 9: IFNGR and IFNA6 reductions was more modest than observed with IFNK and IFNE.

17 Figure 10: IFNGR1 expression was modestly reduced, while IFNAR1 was weakly transcriptionally active.

18 Figure 11: IRF1, IRF4 and IRF8 expression was reduced or silenced, and IFNAR2 was not
19 transcriptionally active.

20 Figure 12: A putative mechanism of immunoevasion in TNBC through interferon silencing.

21 Figure 13: Immunoevasion featured IFIT2 and IFIT3 silencing.

22 Figure 14: Immunoevasion in TNBC through interferon silencing included IFI16, IFI44 and IFI44L, IFITM10
23 and IFIT5 as well as ISG20L2.

24 Figure 15: Innate immune: ADAR and IFIH1 were also silenced. Innate immune: ADAR and IFIH1 were
25 also silenced.

26 **Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC**

27 Figure 16: Expression of MR1 and MICB was not significantly different as compared to the normal breast,
28 but MICA was mildly reduced, as well as CD1a, CD1b, and CD1d.

Figure 17: Expression of Class II transcriptional activator CIITA was very modestly reduced but this was
not considered significant.

Figure 18: TAP2 was silenced, ERAP1 was repressed, but ERAP2 was not affected.

1 Figure 19: Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC is characterized by loss of class I transcriptional activator
2 NLRC5.

3 Figure 20: Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC was also characterized by virtual loss or significant
4 reduction in all classical MHC class I receptors of the HLA family whose expression was measured by
5 RNA-sequencing.

6 **Innate immune evasion in TNBC**

7 Figure 21: NLRC4 was silenced, while expression of NLRP7 and NLRP3 was significantly reduced.

8 Figure 22: Nucleic acid sensor RIG-I (DDx58) was repressed.

9 Figure 23: Virtually the entire TLR family was silenced or significantly transcriptionally repressed, including
10 TLR3, TLR1 and TLR2 and TLR8.

11 Figure 24: Expression of the DNA sensor absent in melanoma 2, AIM2, was completely lost in human
12 TNBC.

13 Figure 25: DNA sensor Zbp1 was repressed.

14 Figure 26: A network of immunoglobulin receptors silenced in triple negative breast cancer, which includes
15 Vsig4, LAIR1, and MILR1.

16 Figure 27: ILDR1 and LRIG1 were instead activated.

17 **Exhaustion in the primary tumor in TNBC.**

18 Figure 28: Themis2 was silenced while Batf was activated; Eomes expression was not significantly
19 altered.

20 Figure 29: TOX modulation in TNBC.

21 Figure 30: TOX modulation was accompanied by changes in CTLA4, near complete silencing of PD-L1, as
22 well as silencing or repression of CD274 (PD-1), TIGIT, HAVCR2 (Tim-3) and AHR.

23 Figure 31: BTLA expression was also significantly reduced, while LAG3 expression was not significantly
24 changed as compared to normal breast.

25 **The immunologic synapse in TNBC.**

26 Figure 32: CD84, CD72, and CD80 were significantly reduced.

27 Figure 33: Loss of immunosurveillance: This was characterized by silencing of cell surface receptors and
28 coreceptors that facilitate productive signaling at the immunologic synapse in T cells and in NK cells,
including CD4, CD300lg, CD163, CD226, CD86, CD14, CD180, CD3g, CD38, CD53, and CD2.

Figure 34: Reduced expression of natural killer activation marker NKG7.

Figure 35: Significant reduction in KIR3DL2 and KIR3DX1.

Figure 36: TNBC transcriptome was otherwise characterized by general loss of killer cell receptor
expression.

Figure 36: Immunodeficiency in TNBC in humans was characterized by silencing of cell surface receptors
and coreceptors that facilitate productive signaling at the immunologic synapse in T cells and in NK cells,
including CD4, CD300lg, CD163, CD226, CD86, CD14, CD180, CD3g, CD38, CD53, and CD2.

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Figure 37: Loss of immunosurveillance in humans with TNBC.

Discussion

We provided here for the first time a systems biologic description of the immunologic landscape in triple negative

1 breast cancer in humans (TNBC).

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28 Methods

We used R-based computational methods and RNA-sequencing (GSE185645) for this study.